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Use of *Arthrobotrys* spp. in biocontrol of the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita*

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ABSTRACT: Plant parasitic nematodes are well-known and devastating pathogens of many agricultural crops around the world. Among the plant phytoparasitic, root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) are the economically important limiting factors in agricultural productivity and the quality of crops. One of the most destructive species of root-knot nematodes is *Meloidogyne incognita* among the most important plant pests which cause severe problems in economically important crops such as vegetables, fruits, and ornamental plants. Root-knot nematodes can be managed by resistant cultivars, crop rotation, cultural practices, chemical nematicides and biocontrol agents. However, the use of nematicides can cause significant problems, including environmental pollution and long-term residue issues. Therefore, biological control with fungus is agriculturally useful an exciting and rapidly developing research area and especially there is growing attention to the exploitation of fungi for the control of nematodes. Nematophagous fungi are an important group of soil microorganisms that can suppress the populations of plant parasitic nematodes. These fungi can be divided into four main categories: endoparasitic fungi, nematode-trapping fungi, fungi that parasitic egg and female, and toxin-producing fungi. Among the nematophagous fungi, nematode-trapping fungi which are natural enemies of nematodes are the most studied. The nematode-trapping fungi develop hyphal structures, such as hyphal, knobs, hyphal rings or branches, adhesion or mechanical capture. *Arthrobotrys* spp. are a well-known nematode-trapping fungus with biocontrol potential against root-knot nematodes, including *M. incognita*. The objective of this paper is to summarize the data on the potential for use of *Arthrobotrys* spp. in biocontrol of the root-knot nematode *M. incognita*.

Keywords: *Arthrobotrys*; Biocontrol; *Meloidogyne incognita*; Root-knot nematode.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nematodes are non-segmented roundworms that live in various habitats and are important for ecology and agricultural economy [1]. They interact with many different organisms in many food webs in a few ways, influence physical processes such as decomposition, carbon and nutrient cycling, and are used for biomonitoring or indicating broader ecosystem properties such as resilience, evolutionary hotspots, energy or nutrient transfers

[2]. According to studies, approximately 26,000 nematode species have been reported so far, with 4100 of them being plant parasites [3].

Nematode damage on plants has a high economic value. However, plant-parasitic nematodes (PPNs) are a serious threat to crops, causing an estimated annual yield loss of over 215 billion \$US worldwide [4]. Root-knot nematodes (RKNs; *Meloidogyne* spp.) (Heteroderidae, Tylenchida) are the most yield-limiting group of PPNs. RKNs are obligate sedentary endoparasites which can easily reproduce in roots of over 5.500 plant species [5]. On the other hand, RKNs are the most extensively distributed in tropical and subtropical countries, and their population in the soil increase easily under appropriate temperature, host and soil conditions. RKNs prefers to sandy loam soils and are more threatening in tropical climates than in temperate climates [6]. The infective second-stage juveniles (J2) enter to plant roots and feed on the roots, they trigger a proliferation process of the attacked cells, and cause swellings (root knots) that can be easily seen. Furthermore, wilting, stunting, and chlorotic symptoms were easily visible in the affected plants' foliar parts [7]. Besides, the injury caused by RKNs during the root penetration process facilitates the invasion of other harmful microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi [8].

Arthrobotrys spp. are a well-known nematode-trapping fungus with biocontrol potential against root-knot nematodes, especially *M. incognita* [9]. The objective of this paper is to summarize the data on the potential for use of *Arthrobotrys* spp. in biocontrol of the root-knot nematode *M. incognita*.

2. MELOIDOGYNE INCOGNITA NEMATODE AND IMPORTANCE OF BIOCONTROL

The genus *Meloidogyne* have 105 described species in the world, the most common of which are *Meloidogyne incognita*, *M. javanica*, *M. arenaria*, *M. chitwoodi*, *M. fallax* and *M. hapla* [10,11]. *Meloidogyne incognita* belongs to the Nematoda: Heteroderidae (Table 1) and is responsible for 8 to 25% yield losses in agricultural crops worldwide [8].

Table 1. Taxonomic classification of *Meloidogyne incognita* [37].

Taxonomic ranks	
Domain	Eukaryota
Kingdom	Metazoa
Phylum	Nematoda
Class	Secernentea
Order	Tylenchida
Sub-order	Tylenchina
Superfamily	Tylenchoidea
Family	Heteroderidae
Subfamily	Meloidogyninae
Genus	<i>Meloidogyne</i>
Species	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i> (Kofoid & White, 1919) Chitwood 1949

Meloidogyne incognita is a serious threat to the agricultural production and economy in tropical and subtropical areas of the world, particularly to vegetable crops, including tomato [12]. For instance, a study on tomato plants infested with *M. incognita* caused a reduction in yield and productivity of about 27% [13]. *M. incognita* has a very broad host range, and once introduced, it is difficult to control. Several strategies have been employed to control *M. incognita* induced crop damage, including biological control, crop rotation, chemical

nematicides, the use of resistant cultivars and integrated pest management. For many years, the use of chemical nematicides has been the first choice for controlling this nematode [14]. However, chemical nematicides may cause human health problems, the destruction of natural pest enemies, the transformation of previously harmless species into pests, harm to non-target species, persistence in the food chain, and environmental pollution [14, 15-17]. The majority of conventional chemical nematicides have been banned or restricted in use recently. As a result, an immediate and effective method of controlling *M. incognita* is required [18]. Some of the environmentally friendly treatments that have been studied for their efficacy against RKN include the use of live microbes (bacteria, fungi, etc.) and/or their secondary metabolites, essential oils, plant extracts, individual and mixed acids such as organic and amino acids, natural bioactive substances, green manure, and industrial wastes. Biocontrol agents such as fungi and bacteria are considered as environmental alternative methods for the management of RKNs [19]. Biological control agents for RKN management have gained popularity in recent years, as has the biopesticide market and interest in microbial control research [20]. Among biological control agents, fungi have different suitable strategies for controlling RKN. There are many kinds of nematophagous (nematode-feeding) fungi which capture and kill nematodes in soil [9].

3. NEMATOPHAGOUS FUNGI AND USING OF *ARTHROBOTRYS* SPP. IN BIOCONTROL OF *MELOIDOGYNE INCOGNITA*

Nematophagous fungi have been studied as a source of biological nematodes in order to reduce the significant economic damage caused by plant-parasitic nematodes due to their association in the rhizosphere. More than 700 nematophagous fungi species have been described [21]. There are four main groups of nematophagous fungi categorized based on their mechanisms of attacking nematodes; (1) the nematode-trapping fungi (about 380 species) that use specialized trapping devices to capture free-living nematodes (*Arthrobotrys* sp., *Drechlerella* sp., *Nematoctonus* sp.), (2) the endo-parasitic fungi (about 120 species) that use adhesive spores to infect nematodes (*Drechmeria* sp.), (3) the egg- and cyst-parasitic fungi that infect these stages with their hyphal tips (*Pochonia* sp., *Lecanicillium* sp.), and (4) the toxin-producing fungi (about 270 species) that secrete a toxin that immobilizes nematodes prior to hyphae penetration through the nematode cuticle (*Pleurotus* sp.) [9,22].

Many soil-dwelling fungus, particularly *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, *Trichoderma harzianum*, *Fusarium* spp., *Pochonia* spp., *Chlamydosporium*, *Aspergillus* spp., and *Penicillium* spp., have been proven to be effective biological control agents [23]. Nematode-trapping and endoparasitic fungi occupied more than 73-76% of total research efforts focusing on PPNs natural enemies and antagonists [24]. Nematode-trapping fungi are found in all regions of the world, from the tropics to Antarctica [25]. They are commonly found in soils and decaying leaf litter, and wood, dung, compost and mosses [21].

The majority of nematode-trapping fungi are asexual taxa, mostly known as hyphomycetes; they are found in Zygomycota, Ascomycota and Basidiomycota, including species in the genera *Arthrobotrys*, *Cystopage*, *Dactylellina*, *Dactylella*, *Drechlerella*, *Hohenbuehelia*, *Hyphoderma*, *Monacrosporium*, *Nematoctonus*, *Orbilia*, *Stylopage*, *Tridentaria*, *Triposporina*, and *Zoophagus* [9,21,25]. Members of the Orbiliaceae (Ascomycota) represent the largest group of nematode-trapping fungi, which include about 96 species and are currently assigned to the asexual genera *Arthrobotrys* (53 species), *Dactylellina* (28 species), and *Drechlerella* (14 species) [9,25].

Hyphae of nematode-trapping fungi form trapping structures with an adhesive to catch the nematodes. The most common structures are three-dimensional adhesive nets of *Arthrobotrys* spp. The fungal hyphae form

rings that constrict upon nematode passage, and the hyphae then penetrate the cuticle and feed on the nematode [26].

Arthrobotrys oligospora is a well-known and extensively studied nematophagous fungus that is regarded as the model of the nematode-trapping fungus. Because of the presence of a variety of trapping structures with functional nematode-capturing devices, it is also well-studied in laboratory conditions as a biocontrol agent [27]. In the studies of the fungus against root-knot nematodes under glasshouse conditions indicated that *A. oligospora* offers a good opportunity to be used as a potential biocontrol agent against *M. incognita* in tomato [7, 28-31]. Furthermore, adding *A. dactyloides* to the soil at an early stage of tomato plant development protects against *M. incognita* penetration for 10 weeks [32], which is long enough to prevent major plant damage. There has been great promise and much research in the use of nematode-trapping fungi *Arthrobotrys* species for the biocontrol of *M. incognita* (Table 2).

Table 2. Examples of *Arthrobotrys* species used for biocontrol of the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* in a variety of crops.

<i>Arthrobotrys</i> species	Crops	References
<i>A. conoides</i>	Tomato	[38]
<i>A. dactyloides</i>	Faba bean	[39]
<i>A. dactyloides</i>	Peanut	[40]
<i>A. dactyloides</i>	Tomato	[32]
<i>A. dactyloides</i>	Soil	[41]
<i>A. irregularis</i>	Tomato	[34,35]
<i>A. musiformis</i>	Tomato	[38]
<i>A. oligospora</i>	Cucumber	[42]
<i>A. oligospora</i>	Okra	[43]
<i>A. oligospora</i>	Tomato	[7, 27-30]
<i>A. oligospora</i>	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	[33]
<i>A. robusta</i>	Tomato	[38]
<i>Arthrobotrys</i> spp.	Tomato	[44,45]

Furthermore, the application of *A. oligospora* against the root-knot nematode *M. incognita* has a significant impact on plant growth parameters [28-31, 33]. The increase in plant growth parameters may be referred to as affecting the root system by the fungus application as the root system became more effective in water and nutrient uptake and transition. There is an immediate need to develop some efficient mass production system of the fungi at a commercial scale for field application if *A. oligospora* is to be widely used as biological control agent against RKNs. Although the potential for use of the nematode-trapping fungi *Arthrobotrys* is high there have been few successes resulting in commercial products (Table 3).

Table 3. Commercial biological nematicides based on *Arthrobotrys* spp.

Products	Country of origin	<i>Arthrobotrys</i> spp.	References
Royal 350	France	<i>A. irregularis</i>	[46]
Royal 300	France	<i>A. robusta</i>	[46]
Adx-1004	Egypt	<i>A. dactyloides</i>	[40]
REM G®	Italy	<i>Arthrobotrys</i> spp.	[47]

Arthrobotrys irregularis has been tested for management of *M. incognita* on tomato. A commercial product based on *A. irregularis*, Royal 350, was used in pot and field experiments [34,35], as well as in the laboratory [34]. Sterilized soil was used in the pot experiment, and *Arthrobotrys* was applied 40 days before planting and inoculation with *M. incognita* J2s. In field tests, the fungus was applied to soil infested with *M. incognita*. Both researchers used the same dose (140 g/m²) and achieved significant control. It is necessary to improve some efficient mass production system of the fungi at a commercial scale for field application.

4. CONCLUSION

Controlling RKNs is usually difficult due to being polyphagous and their high reproduction rate and short generation time [36]. However, biocontrol agents such as *Arthrobotrys* spp. fungi provide long-term and effective solutions against RKNs. Furthermore, the fungi promote plant growth in the plants that they colonize, resulting in a beneficial double effect. Plants will be better protected against RKNs in the long run if biological control agents are used in conjunction with other management strategies as part of an Integrated Pest Management (IPM) program. To protect the environment and human health from chemical pesticides, commercial bio-nematicides can be developed for global use. Isolating indigenous strains is the best way to ensure the success of these biological control agents because they are then adapted to the pest and the environment in which they will be used. The formulation of these strains should be developed to ensure both good microorganism conservation and high effectiveness against pests. On the other hand, the most significant impediment we face is the bureaucracy of product registration.

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